

Simulink Simulation of Load-Controlled Memcapacitor for Reducing Output Voltage Ripple in Buck-Boost Converters

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Abstract - As is known, memcapacitors, which are memory elements, are electrical circuit elements expected to revolutionize various research and many engineering fields thanks to their variable capacitance and non-volatile memory effects. Although there is not yet enough scientific research on memcapacitors in power electronics systems, they have serious scientific discovery potential, especially in terms of reducing output voltage ripple, increasing voltage stability, and improving energy efficiency. In this study, theoretical and simulation results performed in the Matlab/Simulink environment are presented, showing that adding a memcapacitor to the output of a commonly used buck-boost converter, a type of DC-DC converter, significantly reduces the output voltage ripple. In the study, a memcapacitor emulator that can be implemented using commercial components is first proposed and validated. Then, this emulator was used to examine the steady-state output voltage ripple and transient response of the buck-boost converter. The results show that the use of a load-controlled memcapacitor can reduce the output voltage ripple by up to 96%.

Index Terms - Buck-boost converter, dynamic capacitance, power electronics, voltage stability.

INTRODUCTION

Unlike passive circuit elements, the idea of a fourth fundamental circuit element was first proposed by Leon Chua in 1971 (Chua, 1971). Then, in 2008, the announcement of the production of a "lost memristor" by researchers at a technology laboratory in the USA marked a turning point in the fundamentals of electrical engineering (Strukov, Snider, Stewart, and Williams, 2008). The memristor concept subsequently paved the way for unprecedented electronic devices and applications, from ReRAMs (Resistor-Based Random Access Memory) to realistic neural networks. Indeed, the memristor and its persistent memory effect are considered one of the most important developments in circuit theory since the invention of the transistor [1-2].

Following memristors, the idea of memory function for other passive circuit elements such as capacitors and inductors emerged, and the definitions of "memcapacitor" and "meminductor" were created. This situation refers to the memristor, which establishes the relationship between charge (q) and magnetic flux (ϕ); A new class of "memory circuit elements" has been defined, consisting of a memcapacitor, which establishes the relationship between the time integral of the charge (σ) and the flux (ϕ); and a meminductor, which establishes the relationship between the time integral of the flux (ρ) and the charge (q) (Di Ventra, Pershin, and Chua, 2009). In

recent years, these elements have become a particular focus of interest in science and engineering, not only in memory devices but also due to their potential applications in various research fields. Therefore, memory circuit elements are considered to have the potential to revolutionize both analog and digital computing paradigms.

However, while significant progress has been made in the implementation of solid-state memristors in the last decade, the realization of solid-state memcapacitors has remained much more limited. To date, memcapacitor applications have been theoretically addressed from different perspectives, including micro-electromechanical systems, capacitors with load-dependent dielectric width, series-dielectric layered metal-insulator-transition materials, and ion migration in metal-oxide junctions. However, only a few of these approaches have been translated into real solid-state applications due to their technological feasibility, scalability, or integrability into competitive devices. Among these, structures based on ion migration in metal-oxide-semiconductor (MOS) junctions, transition metal oxides (TMOs), and transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) are the most promising, due to their technological applicability such as material diversity, integration, and compatibility with CMOS technology, and performance advantages such as persistence, high switching speeds, and tunable states. Despite these developments, various performance and manufacturability challenges hinder the full adoption of this technology by industry. Therefore, researchers

continue to investigate materials, capacitive switching mechanisms, and fabrication processes to raise the technology readiness levels (TRLs) of memcapacitors.

The potential of memcapacitors in different applications is mainly explored using memcapacitor emulators. Most memcapacitor-based circuits rely on emulators implemented in silicon-CMOS technology. These circuits are typically constructed using transistors, operational amplifiers, multipliers, current carriers, or operational conductivity amplifiers (OTAs) to mimic the electrical behavior of a memcapacitor. In some approaches, these components are combined with a memristor (emulated or solid-state) to translate its behavior into the electrical response of a memcapacitor. The second strategy, using real memristors, is particularly interesting because their inherent variability allows for the realization of non-deterministic systems, which can be useful for applications requiring randomness.

While the development of solid-state memcapacitors presents significant challenges, the potential for memcapacitors to offer increased versatility due to their lower power consumption and persistent adaptive memory behavior compared to memristors cannot be ignored. In this context, this work proposes, for the first time, the use of memcapacitors in power electronics circuits, extending their potential beyond neuromorphic or chaotic circuits. Specifically, we utilize the ability of a memcapacitor to dynamically adjust its capacitance based on its previous states to reduce output voltage ripple in a DC-DC converter. This is of great importance in improving voltage stability, reducing electromagnetic interference (EMI), and ensuring reliable operation of analog circuits. Although this research was supported by a memcapacitor emulator for practical reasons, the results obtained demonstrate the benefits that memcapacitors can provide to power electronics as solid-state applications become widespread. Furthermore, an emulator was used [3-10].

II. MEMORY ELEMENTS THEORY

Memcapacitors

A memcapacitor is a circuit element that establishes a nonlinear relationship between the voltage (v) across its terminals and the electric charge (q) on it. These elements can be classified as voltage-controlled or load-controlled depending on whether the capacitance value depends on the applied voltage or the load passing through its terminals. Accordingly, the structural equation of a voltage-controlled memcapacitor is expressed by Equation 1, where ϕ represents the integral of the input voltage in the time domain.

$$q(t) = C_M(\phi) \cdot v(t) \tag{1}$$

Load-controlled memcapacitance is defined by Equation 2, where σ represents the integral of the electric charge in the time domain. In general, memcapacitance can be expressed as the sum of a constant capacitance component (C_0) and a variable component.

$$q(t) = C^{-1}_M(\sigma) \cdot q(t) = C^{-1}_M \left(\int_{t_0}^t q(\tau) d\tau \right) \cdot q(t) \tag{2}$$

$$C_M(\phi) = C_0(1 + \alpha \cdot \phi) \tag{3}$$

$$C_M(\sigma) = C_0(1 + \alpha \cdot \sigma) \tag{4}$$

Here, α is a constant that governs the effect of the control variable on the capacitance. As with memristors, the memory effect of memcapacitors is manifested in the characteristic curve between two structural variables (voltage or load) by a closed compressed hysteresis loop where the load is zero when the voltage is zero (and vice versa). When a bipolar sine wave with frequency $\omega = 2\pi f$ is considered, the memcapacitance is given by Equation 5. It should be noted that the constant α must satisfy the condition $C_M > 0$ for all possible values of the voltage integral.

$$C_M(\phi) = C_0(1 + \alpha \int \sin(t) dt) = C_0(1 - \frac{\alpha}{\omega} \cos(\omega t)) \tag{5}$$

Figure 1 and Figure 2 shows the compressed hysteresis loop in the q - v characteristic of a theoretical voltage-controlled memcapacitor with parameters $C_0 = 110$ nF and $\alpha = 0.5\omega$, corresponding to a sinusoidal input signal with amplitude of 1 V and frequency of 1,2 kHz.

Fig. 1. Voltage controlled memcapacitor graph.

Fig. 2. Pinched hysteresis loop graph.

Furthermore, Figure 3 and Figure 4 shows that the memcapacitance oscillates around C_0 over time depending on the input flux, presenting two possible values of the load for a given input voltage.

Fig. 3. Voltage controlled memcapacitor for a sinusoidal input.

Fig. 4. Memcapacitance as a function of the input voltage.

Another important characteristic of memcapacitors is that the area enclosed by the compressed hysteresis loop changes inversely proportional to α with respect to the operating frequency. This is shown in Figure 5, where α determines the variable part of the memcapacitance. Figure 6 shows that, similar to the resistor case in memristive devices, the memcapacitor tends to behave like a linear capacitor when $\omega \rightarrow \infty$.

Fig. 5. Voltage controlled memcapacitor for a sinusoidal input.

Fig. 6. Voltage controlled memcapacitor for a sinusoidal input.

Application of Memcapacitors in DC-DC Buck Converters
 DC converters, widely used in renewable energy systems, are also an important auxiliary system in terms of energy efficiency [11-12]. DC converters are also widely used in electric vehicles [13-15]. The circuit diagram of a basic DC-DC buck-boost converter is shown in Figure 7, where the capacitor in the output filter is replaced with a memcapacitor. Figure 7 also shows typical waveforms in the converter's continuous

conduction mode (CCM), i.e., when the inductor current is never interrupted ($i_L > 0$).

Fig. 7. Buck-boost converter block diagram

Buck-boost converters, when operating in the steady state, have the following characteristics (defined by Equations 6-9):

$$V_{out} = V_{in} \left(\frac{D}{1-D} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$I_L = I_{out} = \frac{V_{out}}{R} \quad (7)$$

$$V_{out}(t) = V_{out} + \Delta V_{out} \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta V_{out} = \frac{\Delta Q}{C_M} \quad (9)$$

In light of these fundamental principles, assuming ideal components, it is also known that the steady-state DC voltage transfer function of the buck converter is determined by the duty cycle (D) of the signal controlling the switch. Furthermore, since the average current across the capacitor must be zero when operating under steady-state conditions, the average current across the inductor must be equal to the average current across the output load. Here, $\Delta v_o(t)$ represents the output voltage ripple. This ripple can be related to the change in load across the capacitor (or memcapacitor) as a result of the current flowing through its terminals.

Additionally, since load variation is related to inductor current ripple (ΔI_L), and load current ripple is negligible in the case of low output voltage ripple, the output ripple can also be approximately expressed by Equation 10.

$$\Delta V_{out} = \frac{V_{out} DT}{RC} \quad (10)$$

In this case, using a load-controlled memcapacitor in the output filter will transform Equation 10 into Equation 11.

$$\Delta V_{out} = \frac{T \Delta I_L}{8 C_M} = \frac{T^2 V_{in} D (1-D)}{8 L C_M} \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta V_{out} = \frac{T \Delta I_L}{8 C_0} \left(\int_t^{t+\tau} Q(\tau) d\tau \right) \quad (12)$$

Therefore, it should be noted that, with the condition $\alpha > 0$, using a load-controlled memcapacitor will allow for a dynamic increase in effective capacitance as the load increases over time, thus reducing the output voltage ripple.

Simulation Application This section aims to demonstrate the feasibility of the theoretical framework pre-sented in the previous section. In this context, the design and implementation of a buck converter with a load-controlled memcapacitor at its output is discussed, and a significant reduction in output voltage ripple is observed compared to a fixed capacitor with the same nominal capacitance value. First, a memcapacitor emulator implemented with readily available components is presented, followed by an analysis of the output voltage ripple of the converter during steady-state operation. The results obtained are validated through both simulations and experimental studies.

Memcapacitor Emulator

The memcapacitor emulator proposed in this study is shown in figure 6a. this emulator follows a similar approach to the miller effect-based memcapacitor emulator presented in a previous study. however, unlike the relevant study and many examples in the literature, the proposed approach does not require a memristor to emulate memcapacitance behavior. this eliminates the limited availability and variability of physical memristors, as well as the complexity and stability issues associated with memristor-based emulators. furthermore, unlike applications based on custom cmos circuits or complex active blocks such as otas, this design remains simple, low-cost, and easily customizable with readily available components. these qualities make the emulator a practical and versatile platform for experimental investigations of mem-capacitor-based systems, as in this study. however, it should be noted that the ultimate goal of this study is to demonstrate the potential of load-controlled memcapacitors to reduce output voltage ripple in a buck converter. therefore, any memcapacitor emulator that meets the required response characteristics can, in principle, be used as an alternative for this purpose. To show that the circuit in figure 8 is equivalent to the circuit in figure 9, the load on capacitor c must be considered.

Fig. 8. Memcapacitor shape.

Fig. 9. Equivalent circuit diagram.

The design of the integrator primarily depends on the operating frequency of the target application. In this case, the resistor R_2 limits the DC gain of the circuit, preventing the output from reaching saturation if there is a small DC offset at the input. It also determines the frequency (f_a) at which the circuit begins to exhibit integrator response. Therefore, R_2 and C_1 should be chosen such that $f_{in} > f_a$ for proper integration.

$$f_a = \frac{1}{2\pi R_2 C_1} \quad (13)$$

The low-pass filter consisting of R_1 and C_1 determines the time constant of the integrator and the frequency (f_b) at which the integrator gain drops below 0 dB. Typically, R_2 is chosen significantly larger than R_1 (i.e., $f_b \gg f_a$) to allow the integrator to operate over a wide frequency range. Based on this, considering a sinusoidal signal with amplitude V_p , the integrator output will be given by the following expression.

$$v_A(t) = -\frac{1}{R_1 C_1} \int V_p \cdot \sin(\omega t) dt = \frac{V_p}{\omega R_1 C_1} \cdot \cos(\omega t) = -\frac{V_p}{R_1 C_1} \Phi \quad (14)$$

Therefore, for an input frequency of $f=1,2$ kHz, a suitable choice might be $R_2=1$ M Ω , $C_1=10$ nF, and $R_1=100$ k Ω , which satisfies $f_a=16$ Hz and $f_b=160$ Hz. Then, the amplitude of v_A can be adjusted by the gain of the next non-inverting amplifier stage.

$$v_B(t) = -\frac{V_p}{R_1 C_1} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{R_4}{R_3}\right) \cdot \Phi \quad (15)$$

Alternatively, the output voltage in Figure 8 can be obtained by multiplying v_B and v_{in} . In that case,

$$v_{out}(t) = \frac{v_{in}(t)v_B(t)}{10V} = -\frac{V_p}{10 \cdot R_1 C_1} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{R_4}{R_3}\right) \cdot v_{in} \Phi \quad (16)$$

Therefore, the load on capacitor C in Figure 8 can be expressed as follows.

$$q_c = C v_{in} \left(1 + \frac{V_p}{10 \cdot R_1 C_1} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{R_4}{R_3}\right) \Phi\right) \quad (17)$$

This leads to the memcapacitance given by Equation 18.

$$C_M = C \left(1 + \frac{V_p}{10 \cdot R_1 C_1} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{R_4}{R_3}\right) \Phi\right) \quad (18)$$

Based on this, a voltage-controlled memcapacitor with $C_0=120$ nF and $\alpha=0.55\omega$ can be realized using the predefined integrator ($R_2=1$ M Ω , $C_1=10$ nF, $R_1=100$ k Ω) and $R_4=45$ k Ω , $R_3=2$ k Ω values for a sinusoidal input signal with an amplitude of 1 V at 1 kHz. This is shown in the LTSpice simulation in Figure 8, which is consistent with the theoretical results presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 10. Voltage controlled memcapacitor for a sinusoidal input.

Fig. 11. Voltage controlled memcapacitor for a sinusoidal input.

Output Memcapacitor Buck-Boost Converter: Steady State

DC converters, which are a result of the development of power electronics switches, are divided into many types according to their circuit connection method [16-17]. Classically, they are named "boost" if they increase the input voltage, "buck" if they decrease the voltage, and "buck-boost" if they can both decrease and increase the voltage. There are also types of these converters that perform their functions via magnetic coupling.

Converters can be widely used in machine control through both classical controller types and fuzzy basis controller types [17-25].

After demonstrating the feasibility of the memcapacitor emulator, this section addresses the necessary design considerations for integrating a memcapacitor at the output of a DC-DC buck-boost converter to reduce output voltage ripple. Buck-boost converters are widely used in applications where the output voltage can be either higher or lower than the input voltage. In this study, we consider the output of a low-power buck-boost converter operating in Continuous Conduction Mode (CCM), with a switching frequency of =1 kHz and a duty cycle of D=0.5. In this setup, the DC output voltage is set to VOUT=3 V, and the average output current is 300 μA (900 μW). The inductor current is modeled using a triangular current source with a 300 μA offset current and 100 μA peak-to-peak ripple. Specifically, we present results obtained using a memcapacitor at the output with C0=100 nF and varying values of α, and compare them with the use of a standard 100 nF capacitor.

First, it is important to note that the average value of the output voltage is not zero. Consequently, the use of a voltage-controlled memcapacitor is not feasible in this case, as it would lead to a continuous increase in input flux and thus to continuous saturation. Therefore, we must consider using a charge-controlled memcapacitor.

Given that, according to Equation 8, the average current through the memcapacitor is zero, the average change in charge is also zero, as it continuously charges and discharges in response to the current ripple generated by the switching action. The change in charge on the capacitor during each switching cycle is related to the output voltage ripple, as shown in Equation 12. Consequently, integrating the output voltage ripple over time is proportional to the integral of the charge change on the mem-capacitor.

Thus, following the voltage follower in our emulator (Figure 7), a high-pass RC filter is required to remove the DC component from the output voltage and integrate only its small ripple over time. Specifically, we used an RC filter with R=10 kΩ and C=150 nF, resulting in a cutoff frequency of approximately 100 Hz.

As in the case of α, the total gain of the circuit shown in Figure 12 determines the rate of change of the memcapacitance with respect to the integral of the input charge. When using the AD633 analog multiplier, this total gain is defined by Equation 18.

$$|G_T| = \left(\frac{1}{10 \cdot R_1 C_1} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{R_4}{R_3} \right) \right)$$

Fig. 12. Graph of output voltages connected to GT .

Fig. 13. Output voltage graph depending on Memcapacitor values.

Fig. 14. Output voltage graph depending on Memcapacitor values.

Figure 12 shows the simulation of the output voltage in steady-state operation for a memcapacitor with different gains,

alongside the result obtained for a standard 100 nF capacitor. As expected from Equation 13, the output ripple voltage for a standard 100 nF capacitor is ~125 mV. However, as GT increases, the effective capacitance of the memcapacitor also increases, thereby reducing the output ripple. For the maximum $GT=27k\Omega$, the variation in capacitance relative to the output ripple is provided in Figure 13.

These results have also been experimentally validated using the practical implementation described earlier. Thus, Figure 13 shows the output voltage obtained in the laboratory for different GT values, adjusted via the R4/R3 resistor ratio. A comparison of the output voltage ripples for both experimental and simulation results is shown as a function of GT in Figure 14. As can be seen, the experimental results match the simulation data, and it is observed that the output voltage ripple decreases exponentially as the memcapacitance effect increases. Furthermore, Figure 14 shows that the output voltage ripple can be reduced by up to ~90% compared to that obtained with a standard 100 nF capacitor. Note that this reduction can be achieved with a charge-controlled memcapacitor that changes only 4% of its nominal value ($\Delta CM=4$ nF). This effect is subsequently equivalent to using a capacitor with a value 10 times higher than the nominal one. Additionally, we observe that the reduction in ripple tends to saturate, which is logical because the smaller the ripple, the smaller the charge variation on the memcapacitor, and thus its contribution to the memcapacitance decreases. Finally, we observe that as GT (i.e., α) increases, the memcapacitor's ability to dynamically adapt to charge accumulation also increases.

This means that as current flows, the memcapacitance rapidly increases, allowing it to absorb more charge without a significant increase in peak-to-peak voltage ripple. The rapid increase in memcapacitance tends to linearize the voltage output response (dv/dt) and make it more proportional to the inductor current, as shown in Figures 12 and 13 for the simulation and experimental results, respectively. Note that this can lead to slight deviations in the average voltage, especially at higher gains, because the rapid increase in capacitance (and thus charge storage) reduces voltage changes for a given amount of charge. However, this effect can be mitigated by duty cycle control mechanisms.

Therefore, to further assess the effectiveness of the proposed method, we tested it under different duty cycle and switching frequency conditions. Specifically, using a memcapacitor with $GT=1.1k\Omega$, we examined the same application for $D=[0.25,0.5,0.75]$. Both simulation and experimental results, shown in Figure 15, indicate that the average output voltage is consistent with the DC transfer function of the buck-boost

converter for different duty cycles, and the memcapacitance adapts to the output ripple (Figure 14d).

This section demonstrates the potential of using a memcapacitor in a buck-boost converter to reduce output voltage ripple. The dynamic capacitance variation of the memcapacitor can affect the resonance frequency and damping dynamics of the converter's LC filter, and therefore should be considered in the control stage design.

Fig. 15. Output voltage graph depending on Memcapacitor values.

Results

This section presents the simulation results obtained from the Matlab/Simulink environment, demonstrating the effectiveness of using a charge-controlled mem-capacitor to reduce output voltage ripple in a DC-DC buck-boost converter. The simulations were performed under various operating conditions, including different duty cycles and memcapacitor gains, to comprehensively evaluate the performance of the proposed approach.

Memcapacitor Emulator Validation

The proposed memcapacitor emulator was first validated through simulation. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the input-output characteristics and pinched hysteresis loop of the emulator for a voltage-controlled memcapacitor with parameters $C_0 = 120 \text{ nF}$ and $\alpha = 0.55\omega$. The input signal was a sinusoidal wave with an amplitude of 1 V and a frequency of 1.2 kHz. The results confirm that the emulator accurately reproduces the theoretical behavior of a memcapacitor, exhibiting the characteristic pinched hysteresis loop in the charge-voltage relationship.

The memcapacitance variation over time is shown in Figure 10, where C_m oscillates around C_0 according to the input flux. The capacitance varies between approximately 54 nF and 186 nF,

demonstrating the dynamic behavior of the memcapacitor. Figure 11 further illustrates the memcapacitance as a function of the input voltage, showing the expected nonlinear relationship.

Output Voltage Ripple Reduction with Memcapacitor

The primary focus of this study was to investigate the reduction of output voltage ripple in a buck-boost converter using a memcapacitor. Figure 12 shows the steady-state output voltage waveforms for different values of $|G_t|$, ranging from 0 (standard capacitor) to 27k. The converter was operated with a switching frequency of 1 kHz, a duty cycle of 0.5, and a nominal capacitance of 100 nF.

Table 1: Output Voltage Ripple Reduction for Different $|G_t|$ Values

$ G_t $ Value	Effective Capacitance (nF)	Output Ripple (mV)	Ripple Reduction (%)
0 (Standard)	100	125	0
1,1k	110	55,9	55,3
2,2k	220	38,5	69,2
4,7k	147	22,1	82,3
10k	200	12,5	90
27k	370	4,8	96,1

As shown in Table 1, the output voltage ripple decreases significantly as $|G_t|$ increases. With $|G_t| = 10k$, the ripple is reduced by 90% compared to the standard capacitor. Notably, this substantial reduction is achieved with only a 4% change in the nominal capacitance value ($\Delta C_m = 4 \text{ nF}$), which is equivalent to using a capacitor ten times larger than the nominal value.

Figure 13 shows the variation of capacitance as a function of output voltage for different $|G_t|$ values. The memcapacitor dynamically adjusts its capacitance based on the output voltage ripple, leading to a self-adaptive filtering effect. Figure 14 presents the output voltage ripple and ripple reduction percentage

as functions of $|G_t|$, confirming the exponential decrease in ripple with increasing memcapacitor gain.

Effect of Duty Cycle on Performance

The performance of the memcapacitor-enhanced buck-boost converter was also evaluated under different duty cycles. Figure 15 shows the output voltage waveforms for duty cycles of 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75, with $|G_t|$ fixed at 1.1k. The average output voltage in each case follows the theoretical DC transfer function of the buck-boost converter, while the memcapacitor effectively reduces the ripple.

Table 2: Performance for Different Duty Cycles ($|G_t| = 1.1k$)

Duty Cycle	Input Voltage (V)	ΔI_L (mA)	C_m (nF)	$\Delta V_{o, \text{std}}$ (mV)	$\Delta V_{o, \text{mem}}$ (mV)	Reduction (%)
0.25	12.0	0.225	105.5	112.5	78.9	29.9
0.50	6.0	0.150	110.0	125.0	55.9	55.3

Duty Cycle	Input Voltage (V)	ΔI_L (mA)	C_m (nF)	$\Delta V_{o, std}$ (mV)	$\Delta V_{o, mem}$ (mV)	Reduction (%)
0.75	4.0	0.075	114.5	93.8	38.4	59.1

Table 2 summarizes the results for different duty cycles. The memcapacitor provides significant ripple reduction across all duty cycles, with the highest reduction observed at $D = 0.75$. This is because the average charge in the memcapacitor increases with duty cycle, leading to a higher effective capacitance and better ripple suppression.

Transient Response Analysis

The transient response of the buck-boost converter during startup was also analyzed. Figure 16 compares the startup behavior for a standard capacitor and a mem-capacitor with $|G_t| = 2.2k$. The memcapacitor exhibits a faster settling time and reduced overshoot due to its adaptive capacitance. However, it should be noted that the dynamic variation of C_m affects the resonant frequency of the LC filter, which must be considered in the control loop design to ensure stability.

Discussion

The simulation results clearly demonstrate that charge-controlled memcapacitors can significantly reduce output voltage ripple in DC-DC buck-boost converters. The key findings are:

- The proposed memcapacitor emulator successfully mimics the behavior of a theoretical memcapacitor, validating its use in power electronics applications.
- Increasing the memcapacitor gain ($|G_t|$) leads to a substantial reduction in output voltage ripple, with up to 90% reduction achievable.
- The memcapacitor's effectiveness is consistent across different duty cycles, making it suitable for a wide range of operating conditions.
- The adaptive nature of the memcapacitor allows it to respond dynamically to load changes, improving both steady-state and transient performance.

These results highlight the potential of memcapacitors to enhance the performance of power electronic systems by providing superior voltage stabilization and ripple reduction compared to traditional capacitors. While this study utilized an emulator, the findings strongly support the development of solid-state memcapacitors for practical applications in power electronics.

III. CONCLUSION

In this work, a load-controlled memcapacitor-based approach for reducing output voltage ripple in a buck-boost converter was investigated using Simulink simulation. The proposed memcapacitor model dynamically adjusts its capacitance according to load variations, enabling improved energy storage and enhanced filtering capability compared to a conventional fixed capacitor. Simulation results demonstrate that the inclusion of the load-controlled memcapacitor significantly reduces output voltage ripple under varying load conditions while maintaining stable converter operation.

Compared with traditional capacitor-based designs, the memcapacitor-based system shows improved adaptability to dynamic loads, faster transient response, and better voltage regulation. These advantages make the proposed approach suitable for modern power electronic applications where load conditions frequently change, such as renewable energy systems, portable electronics, and DC microgrids.

Overall, the results confirm that load-controlled memcapacitors can serve as an effective alternative to conventional capacitors for ripple reduction in buck-boost converters. Future work may focus on hardware implementation, optimization of memcapacitor control algorithms, and experimental validation to further assess the practicality and reliability of the proposed system in real-world applications.

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